

Abstract

Evaluation of postpartum calcium status in crossbred dairy cows using infrared thermography

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Abstract

Infrared thermography is a contactless method for assessing the pathophysiological status of animals. The crossbred dairy cows are vulnerable to hypocalcemia due to high milk production. In hypocalcemia, there is a decrease in body temperature. The study was conducted to ascertain the utility of IRT for detecting the postpartum health status of crossbred dairy cows. Postpartum cows were monitored daily from the day of calving up to 21 days of postpartum for the incidence of health disorders. The blood calcium, phosphorus and magnesium levels were measured on 0, 1, 3, 5, 7, 14 and 21 days postpartum. Eye and surface temperatures of ear, muzzle, flank, cheek and vulva were measured before morning and evening milking using an infrared camera. Infrared profile of various body regions revealed that eye and vulval temperatures varied significantly from other body parts in normocalcemic cows. Among the various body regions, skin surface temperature of the ear, muzzle and flank regions were significantly lower in subclinical hypocalcemic cows than normocalcemic cows. Based on the findings of the present study it is concluded that IRT can be used as a cow-side method to predict hypocalcemic status in crossbred dairy cows.

Keywords: Infrared thermography, Hypocalcemia, Crossbred cows